

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TEAMWORKING AND INTERACTION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract

The evolution of foreign language education towards an individualized approach, emphasizing student-centered interactions and facilitated by teachers, underscores the pivotal role of team-based learning strategies, fostering communicative competency. Teamworking and interaction between students play crucial role in the model of student-student rather than teacher-student. The role of the teacher is now facilitating and giving the direction in the educational process, adequately organizing interaction between students, which leads to the development of their communicative competency. Interactive strategies as collaborative projects, peer teaching, debates etc. highly valued among researchers and methodologists and with the development of the new model of teaching in the context of FLE more and more methods and theories appear in FLE process.

Keywords: Foreign language education (FLE), facilitating, interactive, teamwork, collaboration.

Literature review

The theme of interactive learning of students is not new theme nowadays. Johnson & Johnson (1981) provided idea that the interactive student-student learning model is the most effective one. Mercer (1995) delves into the guided construction of knowledge through communication between teachers and learners. His work explores how the learning process discourse among educators and students shapes. Vygotsky's (1978) influential work examines how social interactions and cultural tools shape cognitive development. He emphasizes the role of social context in higher psychological functions. Ghaith (2003) examined the correlation between cooperative learning, student motivation, and academic achievement. This study sheds light on how collaborative methods affects student outcomes. In my earlier work (2023) I suggested the classroom model which provides the idea of independent collaboration of students.

Introduction

In foreign language education, the integration of teamwork and interaction forms the cornerstone of effective learning. Collaborative endeavors within the classroom, whether through group discussions, partner activities, or team projects, provide a dynamic platform for students to engage actively with the language. These interactions not only facilitate the practical application of language skills but also nurture communication abilities, cultural awareness, and linguistic fluency. Through shared experiences and collective participation, learners navigate diverse perspectives, reinforce their understanding of grammar and vocabulary, and develop the confidence needed to express themselves in the target language. Such collaborative environments not only enhance language proficiency but also cultivate a deeper appreciation and understanding of the culture embedded within the language being studied.

Methods:

Effectively organized teamwork and idea communication between students may be the most effective way to develop learners' competencies. Working in a groups give teachers opportunity to be more flexible, give all the students an opportunity to participate in small discussions and engage them. While working with adults individual works may be considered as an effective one, while in classroom it is very important to motivate the students and develop their communicative abilities. As the students are not capable to know everything, they need to collaborate their knowledge and work together to deal with questions, especially in the context of FLE. Teacher, in the student centered classroom, is playing the role of facilitator more than re-translator of information or knowledge, it gradually develop students ability to collaborate, actively search the question and take an action.

By the new format of education, the emotional aim of working in a group is to provide appropriate environment for difficult questions. Students' communicative competence and collaboration may generate ideas more effectively than in individual work. Even the most talented students need some peer collaboration to simplify the task. Interactive learning strategies, including its components develop some students' competences more than other strategies can do (see figure 1). Active interaction means active communication ideas with interaction between students. Communicate idea itself is the subcompetency of globally competent students and refer to the effective communication (verbally and non-verbally) with other participants of the group. Of course, active interaction and communication in class develop students' major competence (Communicative competence) in FLE class.

Figure 1. Reflection of group work to the competencies.

During the active discussion, students may debate inside the group and evaluate each other. It will include all the components of cognitive competency of learners like logical reasoning and critical thinking. Since students work in a group, they have to follow the common aim, work together analyzing and correcting each other's mistakes. Competition plays crucial role in motivating students. The role of competition cannot be overestimated, as students will be more motivated to win the competition. There may be problem that the students will be more preferable to win the competition

rather than get the knowledge. According to Mercer N. (1995) cumulative talk and debate (disputational) focuses more on the communication and the process of talk rather than the developing the idea or working with knowledge than exploratory, which focuses on knowledge. Teacher as a facilitator should find the way to develop contextual competency of the learners. The aspect of competition and peer evaluation are good stimulus for the learners try to do the best. Class should also have both types of peer evaluation, which are in-group and inter-group evaluation (see figure 2).

Student's name	Self-evaluation	In-group evaluation	Other group's evaluation	Final score
Preparation part			X	
Presentation part	X			
Extra evaluation (questions, etc.)				

Figure 2. Example of evaluation list for the group work.

The effectiveness of using teamworking and interaction in class do not mean that all the lessons students should work in a group. It would be better if teacher will allow the learners form the groups or interact with each other if they want it. The given task may be either hard or easy, based on students' ability. As the facilitator, teacher should not set strict rules like do not discuss the question or do not speak in class. If the students are given more chances to interact and find answers to-

gether, they will have big competency of interconnection in the world were the individuals' role became less important. In modern democratic class, students should be able to use all the means of educational process including teachers' advice, have access to work in the group or individually based on their requirements, class-time model by Talgatov & Shalkarkyzy gives understanding of the students' in class freedom (see figure 3).

Figure 3. Class-time model

Result:

By the survey among the student where 100 students took part, it was found to what extend students

value objectivity of the students peer assessment (figure 4) and how the students prefer to work in class (figure 5).

Objectivity of peer evaluation

100 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 4. Objectivity of peer evaluation

Do you prefer work in group of individual

100 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 5. How student prefer to work

Discussion:

The outcomes of this research have provided insight into the differences in preferences in types of interaction. As it is provided in the results of the survey, as compared with individual work (31%), group work was more suitable for students (39%) among survey participants. However, according to the answers of the question participants, it can be concluded that everything depends solely on the task itself. Future studies should explore observation of student interaction choices based on individual preferences and characteristics. As we navigate the diverse landscape of student learning styles and preferences, understanding how to tailor interactions to individual needs is key.

Active interaction and competitiveness of the learning process may have a pressure on students. Young learners may have some problems with the interaction between each other, or differences in behavior. Teacher should not force the student to work in a

group or interfere to the process of creating the groups (teacher may only help the students to find the group, if they do not have). Creating the groups by themselves and working in groups, have a good conversations help the students develop their social competency.

To mitigate subjectivity in peer assessment, implementing structured evaluation criteria is crucial. Designing objective rubrics with clear, quantifiable metrics aids in delineating performance levels. Conducting training sessions familiarizes students with assessment criteria and examples, while calibration activities align their perspectives. Anonymity or blind evaluation removes biases, and involving multiple evaluators averages scores for balanced assessments. Structured feedback, teacher oversight, and encouraging peer discussions further refine assessments, ensuring objectivity and fairness in the evaluation process.

Methods of working in a group differs based on the aim of this type of work. Using interaction teacher

may develop knowledge of the students engage them with the help of competition or try to economize the time. For the active developing of the knowledge teacher may form groups to conduct the practical research or do some practical task. As groups formed to make the solution of the problem easier and find the answer together, students form the groups and participate in exploratory talk where everybody try to give ideas and knowledge that they have. In that kind of class students should be extra motivated by teacher not to lose the motivation. Jigsaw method and peer teaching may be very effective to form the knowledge of the students. The Jigsaw method is a cooperative learning strategy where students become "experts" in a specific topic or area of study and then collaborate with peers who specialize in different aspects. Each student's expertise contributes to the overall understanding of a larger concept or topic, fostering teamwork, communication skills, and a deeper comprehension through the sharing and synthesis of information within the group. By "Jigsaw method" students are given only part of the context and should connect and interact with other students to get the full content of the theme. Jigsaw method stands not only for collaborative learning between students it is also process of critical thinking and analyzes of the content.

Conclusion:

The evolution of foreign language education towards an individualized approach underscores the pivotal role of student-student interaction and teamwork in the learning process. This shift places teachers in a facilitative role, orchestrating interactions that foster communicative competency among students. Collaborative projects, debates, and peer teaching emerge as highly valued interactive strategies, driving the development of new methodologies in language education. Embracing collaborative environments not only enhances language proficiency but also cultivates deeper cultural appreciation. Organized teamwork and idea exchange empower learners, encouraging active participation and collaborative problem-solving. However, the integration of group dynamics should balance competition with knowledge development, ensuring that learning isn't eclipsed by the pursuit of victory. The teacher's role as a facilitator is crucial, guiding students

toward constructive discussions and leveraging diverse evaluation methods to motivate and assess group dynamics. Yet, the introduction of teamwork and interaction should accommodate individual preferences, fostering a democratic classroom where students have the freedom to engage collectively or individually, aligning with their needs. Various methods, such as the Jigsaw technique, serve as powerful tools, not just for collaborative learning but also for nurturing critical thinking and content analysis. As foreign language education evolves, embracing teamwork and interaction serves as a catalyst, empowering students to navigate linguistic complexities while fostering a global, interconnected worldview.

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